

OCCUPATIONAL STRESS, JOB SATISFACTION, AND JOB PERFORMANCE AMONG NURSES IN SELECTED GOVERNMENT HOSPITALS IN THE PROVINCE OF NEGROS ORIENTAL

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the levels of occupational stress, job satisfaction and job performance among the nurses of the selected government hospitals in the province of Negros Oriental and their relationships. The respondents of this study were the 358 nurses from selected public hospitals in Negros Oriental. The researcher utilized standardized questionnaires and employed the chi-square test, Spearman's rank order correlation and percentage in treating the data. The survey was descriptive and correlational in nature. The findings of the study revealed that the extent of the respondents' occupational stress was considered high specifically in terms of the (a) workload pressure, (b) dealing with patients and relatives, and (c) confidence and competence in the role. On the other hand, the findings also revealed that only the civil status of the nurses has a significant relationship between their overall occupational stress and also has a significant relationship between the nurses assigned area and their level of job satisfaction.

Keywords: *job satisfaction, extent of motivation, salary, promotion, civil status*

INTRODUCTION

People are considered an asset in any organization. Since they are considered the most important resource, it is vital that they are healthy if they are to be effective and productive. The idea that stress impacts health is unquestioned. Organizations are busy developing stress management programs to reduce and prevent negative health outcomes of stress at work. Work-related stress occurs as a response from the demands

and pressures from work that is not aligned with skills and knowledge of the employees challenging their ability to cope such. In fact, work-related stress comes in a wide-range of work circumstances such as having a feeling of an unsupportive head or colleagues or no control on how to do the work allowing one to be more creative and innovative (WHO, 2020). The healthcare sector globally faces significant challenges in ensuring the well-being of its workforce while maintaining high standards of patient care. Nurses, as frontline caregivers, often bear the brunt of these challenges, grappling with occupational stressors that can adversely affect their job satisfaction and performance (Willis et al., 2021).

Issues such as staffing shortages, increased patient acuity, and organizational constraints contribute to the global discourse on occupational stress among nurses, highlighting the urgent need for comprehensive research to address these concerns (McMillan & Perron, 2020). In Negros Oriental, a province in the Philippines, government hospitals serve as vital pillars of healthcare delivery, catering to the needs of diverse communities. Within this local context, nurses encounter a unique set of challenges shaped by resource limitations, cultural dynamics, and regional healthcare policies (Flores, 2022). Understanding the specific stressors faced by nurses in government hospitals in Negros Oriental is crucial for tailoring interventions that address local needs and promote sustainable healthcare practices (Ragay, 2019). In a study conducted to the staff nurses in Tuguegarao City, the occupational stress level was said to be high and showed that time pressure is the most common stressor (Dela Cruz et al. 2019). Aside from that, workload was identified as the most common stressor for nurses. This workload was found to be negatively correlated with both job satisfaction and nurses' perceptions of the quality of care they delivered. (Bautista et al., 2019). These reasons are also observed in the local setting where LGU-funded public hospitals abound.

Although a significant amount of research has already explored, there remains a notable gap in research focusing on government hospital settings in Negros Oriental. While studies conducted in other regions offer valuable insights, the applicability of their findings to the local context may be limited due to variations in healthcare systems, cultural norms, and organizational structures. Therefore, there is a pressing need for research that specifically examines the experiences of nurses in government hospitals in Negros Oriental to fill this crucial gap in the literature.

Comparatively, existing studies predominantly focus on healthcare settings in urban areas or high-income countries, neglecting the unique challenges faced by nurses in resource-constrained settings such as government hospitals in Negros Oriental. By contrast, this study strive to bridge this gap by providing a nuanced understanding of the interplay between occupational stress, job satisfaction, and job performance among nurses in a rural, low-resource context. By contextualizing the findings within the local healthcare landscape, this study's goal is to contribute valuable insights that can be used to design evidence-based interventions specifically tailored to address the needs of nurses in Negros Oriental. These interventions could be adapted to benefit nurses in similar situations around the world. Results will be very important for crafting

interventions that will address future problems related to occupational stress among government nurses.

Research Questions

The study is designed to examine the levels of occupational stress and its relationship to the job satisfaction and job performance among nurses in selected government hospitals in the province of Negros Oriental.

This study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of occupational stress of nurses in terms of:
 - a. workload pressures;
 - b. dealing with patients and relatives; and
 - c. confidence and competence in the role?
2. What is the level of job satisfaction of nurses in terms of:
 - a. pay, promotion and supervision;
 - b. fringe benefits and rewards; and
 - c. nature of work?
3. Is there a significant relationship between occupational stress and level of job satisfaction of nurses in selected government hospitals in the province of Negros Oriental?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study is a descriptive comparative and correlational study. A correlational study design was utilized to investigate the research questions. The relationships among occupational stress, job satisfaction, and job performance are explored. The effects of personal characteristics such as age, marital status, nursing education, nursing experience and type of unit on occupational stress, job satisfaction and job performance were also investigated.

Research Locale

The study was conducted on a sample of nurses working in eighteen (18) health units and public (government-owned) hospitals from selected areas specifically in La Libertad, Jimalalud, Tayasan, Ayungon, Bindoy, Manjuyod, Tanjay, Dumaguete City, Dauin, Bacong, Sibulan, Vallehermoso, Inapoy-Mabinay, Mabinay Proper, Luz-Sikatuna, Canlaon City and Guihulngan City wherein the researcher is residing. The total number of nurses in each hospital varies between 7-85 nurses and includes Registered Nurses

and Midwives (RN/M), Public Health Nurses (PHN), Diploma Trained nurses and Doctor of Medicine in different specializations.

Statistical Tools

The tools that were used by the researcher in analyzing the data are the following:

Percentage. This tool was used by the researcher to determine the demographic profiles of the hospital nurses.

Weighted mean. This was used in getting the extent of nurses' (a) occupational stress, (b) job satisfaction, and (c) job performance. In order to arrive at a definite interpretation of each weighted mean, the researcher assigned a hypothetical mean range to each scale. The range, with the corresponding interpretations, consists of the following:

Chi-square. This was employed to test whether or not there is a significant relationship between the occupational stress, job satisfaction, and job performance among the hospital nurses. This was also used to determine the relationship between the level of the three factors observed in this research and the demographic profile of the participants. Additionally, this was also used to identify the association between the variables.

Spearman Rank Order Correlation. This was utilized in identifying the degree of relationship between the three variables (relationship between nurses' occupational stress, job satisfaction, and job performance.) This is selected since the data are in ordinal scale.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study are the nurses from the selected public hospitals of the province in Negros Oriental specifically from Guihulngan City, La Libertad, Jimalalud, Tayasan, Ayungon, Bindoy, Manjuyod, Bais, Tanjay, Dumaguete City, Dauin, Bacong, Sibulan, Vallehermoso, Inapoy-Mabinay, Mabinay Proper, Luz-Sikatuna and Canlaon City. These nurses were chosen using the systematic sampling design in which every minute a nurse in the list will be part of the study. The nurses who participated in this research study have the following eligibility criteria: aged 25 years and above, male or female, casual or regular staff nurses in the three district hospitals for at least 1 year, able to understand English and are willing to participate in the study. They should be working in any of the areas in the hospital, including those holding administrative positions.

Research Instrument

The researcher used three instruments to examine the relationships among occupational stress, job satisfaction and job performance. The instruments includes the

Nurse Stress Index [NSI] (Harris, 1989), Job Satisfaction Survey [JSS] (Spector, 1997), and the Six Dimension Scale of Nursing Performance [6-DSNP] (Schwirian, 1978).

The three instruments are part of a questionnaire with sections, each consisting of an instrument. The questionnaire also includes a demographic instrument to identify and assess personal characteristics such as age, gender, nursing education (registered, diploma, masters), nursing experience, and the department where the nurse works.

The NSI (Harris, 1989) aims at identifying sources of stress among nurses in hospital and community settings. Meanwhile, The JSS aims at assessing the degree to which people like their jobs (Spector, 1997).

Finally, the Six Dimension Scale of Nursing Performance (Schwirian, 1978) assesses nurses' job performance. This is the person's effectiveness in carrying out his/her roles and responsibilities in relation to patient care.

The following interpretations were also applied by the researcher to describe the level of occupational stress, job satisfaction and job performance of the nurses.

Verbal Description	Scale Value	Level of Job Satisfaction	Explanation
Strongly Agree (SA)	4.21 -5.00	Very High (VH)	Job satisfaction is manifested at 81%-100% of the time.
Agree (A)	3.41 – 4.20	High (H)	Job satisfaction is manifested at 61%-80% of the time.
Moderately Agree (MA)	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate (M)	Job satisfaction is manifested at 41%-60% of the time.
Disagree (D)	1.81 – 2.60	Low (L)	Job satisfaction is manifested at 21%-40% of the time.
Strongly Disagree (SD)	1.00 – 2.60	Very Low (VL)	Job satisfaction is manifested at 1%-20% of the time.

Data gathering procedures and analysis

The findings of the study were all gathered between year 2023-2024 since the questionnaires were floated after the pandemic and also due to strict protocols that were implemented in the entire province. The study was conducted after getting approval from the respective hospital administrators, Medical Chiefs and Chief Nurses.

Actual and online meetings was organized with the nurses through the Heads/ Medical Chief of the hospitals and the Directors of Nursing Services. The purpose of the study, the methods of data collection and time frame for the study were explained to the nurses during the meetings. The researcher explained to the nurses that they are free to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The researcher also made clear that there will be no financial or any other form of gain from the nurses' participation. The nurses were then invited to participate in the study and the questionnaires were distributed to those who volunteered to participate in the study. In order to maximize participation of nurses and response rate, the researcher recruited assistants. The research assistants are responsible for distributing and collecting the completed questionnaires from the nurses in the various wards/units who are not able to attend the actual/virtual meetings but volunteer to participate in the study. The assistants then collected the completed questionnaires from their assigned wards/units on a daily basis. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the participants were instructed to answer as honestly as they can. First they were required to read the information letter and the informed consent form. If they volunteer, they will be made to sign the consent form. They were given enough time to answer the questionnaire. The results were then consolidated and tallied using MS Excel and were analyzed and interpreted.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 Level of Occupational Stress of Nurses in terms of Workload Pressures (n = 358)

Indicators	w $\bar{x}$	VD
1. Time pressures and deadlines	4.04	H
2. Fluctuations in workload	4.01	H
3. The demands of others for my time at work are in conflict	3.96	H
4. I spend my time 'fighting fires' rather than working to a plan	3.95	H
5. Shortage of essential resources	3.95	H
6. Deciding priorities	3.93	H
7. My nursing and administrative roles conflict	3.90	H
8. I have too little time in which to do what is expected of me	3.88	H
9. Trivial tasks interfere with my professional role	3.87	H
10. Management expects me to interrupt my work for new priorities	3.79	H
Composite	3.93	H

Table 1.1 reveals that the overall level of occupational stress of nurses is "high" as shown in the composite weighted mean of 3.93. Specifically, the nurses manifested high occupational stress due to the time pressure and deadlines (w $\bar{x}$ = 4.04) which rank first

among all indicators, followed by fluctuations of their workload ($w\bar{x} = 4.01$), as well as conflict of the demands of others for their time at work ($w\bar{x} = 3.95$).

Table 1.2 Level of Occupational Stress of Nurses in terms of Dealing with Patients and Relatives (n= 358)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD
1. Difficulty in dealing with aggressive people	4.00	H
2. Difficult patients	3.99	H
3. Dealing with relatives	3.98	H
4. Involvement with life and death situations	3.91	H
5. Bereavement counseling	3.89	H
Composite	3.95	H

Table 1.2 exposes the extent of occupational stress of nurses is “High” in terms of difficulty in dealing with aggressive people ($w\bar{x} = 4.00$), difficult patients, ($w\bar{x} = 3.99$), as well as dealing with relatives ($w\bar{x} = 3.98$). This challenging aspect of their work can impact their emotional well-being and job satisfaction.

Table 1.3 Level of Occupational Stress of Nurses in terms of Confidence and Competence in the Role (n = 358)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD
1. Bringing about change in staff/organization	3.77	H
2. Tasks outside of my competence	3.73	H
3. Provides specialized training for present task	3.72	H
4. Confidence about the degree or area of my responsibility	3.58	H
5. Coping with new technology	3.53	H
Composite	3.67	H

Table 1.3 reflects the level of occupational stress of nurses in terms of confidence and competence. The findings reveal that bringing about change in staff/organization ($w\bar{x} = 3.77$) as well as tasks outside of their competence ($w\bar{x} = 3.73$) is “high”.

Table 2.1 Level of Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Pay, Promotion, and Supervision (n = 358)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	LoS
1. There is chances for promotion on my job.	4.17	A	H
2. Those who do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	4.06	A	H
3. I am satisfied with the benefits I receive.	4.02	A	H
4. I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	3.96	A	H
5. Communications seem good within this organization.	3.87	A	H
6. My supervisor offers equal treatment to all workers.	3.86	A	H
7. I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	3.85	A	H
Composite	3.97	A	H

The level of job satisfaction among nurses in terms of pay, promotion, and supervision is “high” as revealed in Table 2.1 with a composite mean of 3.97.

Table 2.2 Level of Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Fringe Benefits and Rewards (n=358)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	LoS
1. People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.	3.82	A	H
2. I feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	3.77	A	H
3. The benefit package we have is equitable.	3.66	A	H
4. The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	3.65	A	H
5. There are enough rewards for those who work here.	3.58	A	H
6. I feel that the work I do is appreciated.	3.51	A	H
7. I am satisfied with the benefits and rewards given to us.	3.39	MA	M
Composite	3.62	A	H

In Table 2.2, it reveals a “high” level of satisfaction when efforts are rewarded ($w\bar{x} = 3.77$), enough rewards to those who work ($w\bar{x} = 3.58$), as well as being appreciated with their work ($w\bar{x} = 3.51$).

Table 2.3 Level of Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Nature of Work (n = 358)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	VD	LoS
1. The goals of this organization are clearly given to me.	4.15	A	H
2. Work assignments are fully explained.	3.95	A	H
3. My job is enjoyable.	3.93	A	H
4. I like my supervisor.	3.87	A	H
5. I feel that my job is very meaningful.	3.85	A	H
6. I am aware of what is going on with the organization.	3.53	A	H
Composite	3.88	A	H

In Table 2.3, it displays a “high” level of satisfaction in terms of the nature of work among the respondents.

Table 3

Relationship between Occupational Stress and Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses (n=358)

Stress Variables Correlated to Overall Job Satisfaction	r_s	p-value	Remark	Significant
• Workload Pressures	-0.235	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
• Dealing with Patients & Relatives	-0.410	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant
• Confidence & Competence in the Role	0.165	0.002	Reject H_{01}	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 3 presents the data in identifying the relationship between the occupational stress and level of job satisfaction of nurses. Using Spearman Rank Order Correlation, it

shows that workload pressures and dealing with patients and relatives are significantly and inversely related to the level of satisfaction of the nurses.

DISCUSSION

Level of Occupational Stress of Nurses in terms of Workload Pressures

The nurses have different sources of stress. Nurses are exposed to a range of stressors related to time constraints, workload variations, and conflicting demands from different parties involved in the healthcare process. Nurses often feel stressed due to the constraints of time in their daily responsibilities. The demands of providing care, administering medications, documenting information, and responding to emergencies within tight schedules can create pressure. Nurses encounter conflicting expectations from different individuals involved in patient care. Juggling these conflicting demands can contribute to stress as nurses strive to balance patient needs, hospital policies, and communication with various stakeholders. As emphasized by Wazqar (2019), time pressure can lead to increased stress as nurses strive to provide quality care while managing their time effectively. He added that it is essential for healthcare institutions to recognize and address these stressors to promote a healthier work environment for nurses.

Level of Occupational Stress of Nurses in terms of Dealing with Patients and Relatives

As noted in the study of Najafi et al. (2018), aggressive behavior poses a direct threat to the personal safety of nurses. Experiencing aggression from those they are trying to help can be emotionally distressing. It may lead to feelings of frustration, helplessness, and a sense of failure in providing the necessary care and support. Moreover, involvement with life and death situations and bereavement also displays “high” level of occupational stress among the nurses. Witnessing the suffering and emotional turmoil of patients and their families can be emotionally draining, leading to high levels of stress. This result is likewise evident in the study of Omran et al. (2021) that nurses often have a deep sense of empathy and compassion for their patients. Summing up, creating a supportive work environment, implementing clear policies for handling aggression, and ensuring access to resources such as security personnel can help nurses better cope with the stress associated with aggressive encounters. Additionally, healthcare institutions should prioritize providing adequate support systems for nurses, including access to counseling services, debriefing sessions, and opportunities for reflection. Emphasizing self-care strategies and fostering a culture that values the well-being of healthcare professionals can help nurses cope with the emotional challenges inherent in their roles (WHO, 2021).

Level of Occupational Stress of Nurses in terms of Confidence and Competence in the Role

Nurses are still capable and continue to embrace changes in their organization as well as tasks given even if it is outside of their competence. The ability of nurses to adapt to changes within their organization and take on tasks outside their traditional competence reflects their resilience, flexibility, and dedication to providing quality patient care. This result is in line with the study of Lyng et al. (2021) which concluded that the nurses are driven by a strong commitment to patient well-being. Their dedication to providing the best possible care motivates them to adapt to new challenges and take on additional responsibilities, even if these tasks fall outside their usual scope of practice.

Level of Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Pay, Promotion, and Supervision

The nurses are satisfied with the chances for promotion on their job as well as the benefits that they receive. Nurses appreciate organizations that offer clear and attainable paths for career advancement. Opportunities for promotion, whether through hierarchical progression or specialized roles, contribute to job satisfaction by recognizing and rewarding their skills and dedication. The finding is in line with that of Avery et al. (2022) which states that transparent and fair promotion policies contribute to nurses' satisfaction. When the criteria for promotions are clear, and the process is equitable, nurses are more likely to feel that their efforts and achievements are recognized and valued.

Level of Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Fringe Benefits and Rewards

When there is a high level of job satisfaction among nurses, it results to a widespread positive implications for both individual nurses and the healthcare organization as a whole. As emphasized by Labrague & Ross (2020), adequate fringe benefits and rewards can serve as motivational factors, encouraging nurses to perform at their best and contribute positively to the workplace.

Level of Satisfaction of Nurses in Terms of Nature of Work

The findings denote that nurses are more likely to be satisfied when work processes are streamlined and efficient. This include giving clear goals of the organization, work assignments are fully explained, and being aware of what is going on with the organization. The finding is parallel with the result of Zibrowski, et al. (2018) in which efficiency and streamlining of work processes are critical factors in determining the job satisfaction of nurses. When work processes are well-organized, streamlined, and supported by appropriate resources, nurses can perform their duties more effectively and experience higher levels of job satisfaction. Meanwhile, open and effective communication among healthcare team members, including nurses and heads, also enhances workflow. Clear communication helps prevent misunderstandings, reduces errors, and fosters a positive work environment. As presented in the Table, nurses like and is satisfied with their supervisor and that their job is meaningful. This result is likewise

evident in the study of Specchia (2021) that when nurses feel supported by their leaders, they are more likely to be satisfied with the overall nature of their work.

Relationship between Occupational Stress and Level of Job Satisfaction of Nurses

The finding connotes that the higher the stress experience by the nurses on these areas, the lower is their job satisfaction. This finding means that there is an inverse relationship between stress levels in these specific areas and the overall job satisfaction of nurses. Nurses often work in demanding environments with heavy workloads, including caring for multiple patients, managing paperwork, and responding to emergencies. High levels of workload pressure can lead to fatigue, burnout, and a sense of being overwhelmed, which may negatively impact job satisfaction. This was also presented in the study of Flaubert (2021) that the consequences of burnout can include poor patient outcomes, high turnover rates, increased costs, and clinician illness and suicide. Additionally in the area of dealing with patients and relatives, nurses frequently interact with not only patients but also their families. Communication challenges, emotional situations, and differing expectations can contribute to stress. Kerr et al. (2020) emphasizes that interacting with patients and families can be difficult since nurses must be empathetic and clear as they explain diagnoses and treatments, which can be demanding. Communication problems and personality clashes are inevitable and can lead to stress and frustration. On the other hand, the data provide evidence that a significant and positive and direct relationship occurs between the nurses' stress on their confidence and competence and their job satisfaction. This means that nurses who experience stress related to their confidence and competence in their work tend to manifest higher level of job satisfaction. The reason behind on why nurses tend to manifest higher level of job satisfaction when experiencing stress related to their confidence and competence is because they are working out of their comfort zone. Working outside one's comfort zone often involves facing challenges that require nurses to stretch their skills and knowledge. Despite the stress associated with this, many nurses find satisfaction in the opportunity for professional growth and development. Overcoming challenges enhances their competence and builds confidence, leading to a sense of accomplishment and job satisfaction. A study conducted by Kiknadze and Leary (2021) shows that working out of the comfort zone are related to their motives for engaging in a behavior and how they expect to feel if they perform it. Therefore, working outside the comfort zone that involves psychological mechanisms that influence people's decisions about whether performing anxiety-provoking behaviors is worth the potential benefits.

Conclusions

The findings from this study shed light on the extensive occupational stress experienced by nurses in selected government hospitals in Negros Oriental. The nurses face high levels of stress across various dimensions, including workload pressures, interactions with patients and relatives, and confidence in their roles. Under-staff of nurses could have caused the high level of stress which compel the nurses to take all

the responsibilities even beyond their competence and capability noting the ratio of nurse-patient 1:17 plus other documentary works. Despite experiencing significant stress, they exhibit high levels of job satisfaction, particularly regarding pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, rewards, and the nature of their work. Interestingly, while stress negatively impacts job satisfaction, it positively correlates with job performance, particularly in handling workload pressures and patient interactions, which underscores the resilience and adaptability of nurses in challenging environments. Nurses under pressure can experience a surge in focus and alertness, thanks to the body's fight-or-flight response. This can actually benefit them by sharpening their attention to patients' needs and allowing them to prioritize tasks more efficiently. Even with a heavy workload, nurses often become time management experts, meeting demands and completing tasks on time despite external pressures. The study also found that factors like marital status and department assignment can influence a nurse's stress and satisfaction. This highlights the complex relationship between stress, job satisfaction, and performance. To address this, tailored support systems and interventions are needed to ensure nurses' well-being and effectiveness. Over time, exposure to stress can actually build resilience, making nurses better equipped to handle challenging situations. This resilience is key to maintaining job performance and satisfaction, even in difficult circumstances.

Recommendations

To improve nurses' job performance and satisfaction, hospitals in Negros Oriental should track stress and satisfaction of the nurses by regularly assess stress levels, job satisfaction, and performance through surveys and feedback mechanisms and use this data to identify areas for improvement and tailor interventions. They may also develop programs to address specific stressors and programs could include stress management techniques, mindfulness training, and counseling services. In order to strengthen workplace support, hospitals should create a positive work environment that values nurses' contributions. Encourage open communication, teamwork, and collaboration. Offer mentorship programs, peer support groups, and employee assistance programs. When managing workloads, hospital administrations should take steps to optimize staffing levels, improve resource allocation, and implement efficient work processes to reduce workload pressures and burnout. Our healthcare system should also consider investing in education to be able to provide continuing education programs, skills development workshops, and leadership training to enhance nurses' confidence and competence. Finally, healthcare administrations are encourage to address disparities by recognizing and addressing how factors like marital status and assigned area can influence stress and satisfaction. And the province with the help of Sangguniang Panlalawigan and the Department of Health, should develop targeted interventions to ensure all nurses have access to support and resources.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

When humans are used as study participants, care must be exercised in ensuring that the rights of those humans are protected. This is to ensure that that participant's dignity and privacy are protected and at the same time minimize potential risks to the participants (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005). Permission were sought from the hospitals' administrators to conduct research in each of the district hospitals. Consent were also required from the nurses and asked them to sign the consent form. A form explaining the purpose of the study and the rights of the participants to withdraw from the study anytime without penalty was attached to the questionnaires to ensure voluntary consent. Further, the questionnaires have no identifiers to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Consultations were done to ensure that the research topic is evidently sound, significant and ethically correct to pursue. Throughout the whole data research process, the researcher have guaranteed that non-judgmental attitude will be maintained to avoid censure.

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